

ORGANIZATION OF DATA WAREHOUSES FOR DECISION SUPPORT SYSTEMS

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Abstract: Here was reflected project experience of Data Base for suggestion support system, tailored for historical information storage.

Keywords: Decision support systems (DSS), data warehouses (Data Warehouse), operational data analysis (OLAP), Data Mining (DM), (KDD - knowledge discovery in data bases).

Decision support systems – one of the areas of development of information technology, they provide systematization of information and in-depth analysis in order to optimize operational activities, determine tactical actions and develop a strategy for the development of the system used.

Decision support systems (DSS) are reflected in data warehouses (Data Warehouse) and operational data analysis (OLAP) .

It is advisable to start creating a DSS with the development of a pilot project, within which it was planned to demonstrate the capabilities of Oracle products and technologies for creating a multi-level architecture of data warehouses, loading data from various sources and multidimensional information analysis.

Currently, there is an urgent problem of creating a qualitatively new analytical management system, focused on solving the problems of developing control decisions based on a comprehensive analysis of production situations and forecasting their development in the interests of the formation and implementation of optimal production management modes. AIT used to solve the problem under consideration includes a number of new information and mathematical technologies. The emergence of new technologies for storing and processing data (warehouses or warehouses, data marts) is associated with the need to accumulate and quickly process extremely large volumes of retrospective information (units of GB) [1, 2, 3]. In particular, the need to speed up the processing of analytical queries led to the development of a multidimensional data presentation format and the creation of new

concepts for storing and processing data, presented in the form of the postulates of W. Inmon [4] and E. Codd [5].

Operational analysis of the current situation and its comparison with retrospective analysis data are implemented using OLAP tools (on - line analytical processing) [6]. It is assumed that OLAP technologies can become a powerful tool for rapid visualization of the state of the production situation in the interests of improving the current management of technological processes (TP) and dispatch of material flows.

However, for a deeper understanding of ongoing production processes, it is necessary to conduct appropriate analytical studies based on the use of complex mathematical tools for analyzing multidimensional situations, predicting their development and developing optimizing recommendations. To solve these problems, software and algorithmic data mining tools DM (Data Mining).

Data Mining (DM) (KDD - knowledge discovery in data bases) – the latest direction in the field of information technology, focused on solving problems of decision support based on quantitative and qualitative research; analysis of ultra-large arrays of heterogeneous retrospective and operational data.

The theoretical basis of the project can be the classic works of W. Inmon on data warehouses [7], as well as the rich practical experience accumulated at Oracle Corporation through the implementation of complex DSS systems, as well as a ready-made methodological platform for such projects - the Oracle Data Warehousing Method [8].

a bank's open position and their subsequent analysis was chosen as a model . An open position refers to the key characteristics of an organization's activities, significantly influences the assessment of its general condition and is used when making management decisions.

To analyze an organization's open positions, two main indicators are used - spot position and forward position , each of which can be calculated for each profit center on any date, for any currency and expressed both in the original currency and in its dollar equivalent. These metrics should be calculated based on data obtained from existing online transaction processing systems (OLTP systems). First of all, it is advisable to extract data from the MIDAS DBA systems, running on the AS/400 platform using the DB2/400 DBMS, and FXMM, based on MS SQL Server. From the point of view of end-user analysts, it is of interest both to analyze the actual structure and dynamics of changes in the bank's open position for various currencies and time intervals, and to compare similar indicators obtained from different sources.

To solve the problem, it is enough to organize a multidimensional database, load indicators into it and, using standard multidimensional analysis tools, build the necessary dynamic reports and graphs.

In our case, a specific statement was used to demonstrate the general technology and means of solving any similar problems, i.e. tasks with the following features:

- the need to analyze bank performance indicators that determine management decisions at various levels
- possibility of historical analysis of indicators for any time period
- increased requirements for dynamic analysis capabilities, including ad-hoc reports, various types of information presentation in the form of tables and charts, aggregation of data across any sections, the use of forecasting and modeling methods, flexible means of generating derived indicators based on basic ones, performing analysis using "what-if" scenarios " and etc.
- obtaining indicators based on data accumulated in various OLTP systems; At the same time, the process of analyzing indicators should not affect the performance of already quite loaded operating systems;
- the need to compare and/or harmonize data obtained from different operating systems and external sources

The analyzed indicators are calculated based on data from two operating systems - MIDAS DBA and FXMM, running on different platforms. Some data that is identical in meaning is stored in both one and another system. First of all, this concerns regulatory and reference information - a directory of currencies, a list of profit centers, and in addition, each system uses its own representation of the time period and its own level of detail of actual data.

This requires harmonization of information in order to provide a "single" view of indicators, regardless of the source on which they are calculated. The analyzed characteristics are essentially "multidimensional" in nature: each indicator depends on the date, currency, profit centers, etc. At the same time, it is important to be able to present them in different sections. From a structural analysis perspective, for example, it is interesting to see how an open position is distributed across different currencies. To study dynamic characteristics, you need to imagine how the position changed during a given time interval, etc.

The central component of the system is the data warehouse - a database designed to store historical information downloaded from various operating systems and external sources in a consistent form. A separate RS computer is allocated for the storage, on which Oracle11 Enterprise Edition is installed.

Despite the fact that, from a formal point of view, the repository is a regular database, its design differs in many ways from the construction of an operating system database. A regular database, as a rule, is created according to the following scheme: studying the subject area, building an information model, developing a database project based on it, creating a database. In the case of a data warehouse, the required steps are:

- determining the information needs of users in relation to data accumulated in the database of operational systems - data sources;
- studying local databases of OLTP systems;
- allocating for each such database a subset of data necessary for loading into the storage;
- integration of local data subsets and development of an overall consistent storage schema.

As a tool environment for performing all warehouse design tasks, it is convenient to use the Oracle Designer product or its limited version, Oracle Data Mart Designer, compiled specifically for the development of data marts and warehouses.

The central component of Oracle Designer is the repository - a special database in which all metainformation about the structure and objects of the repository is stored. Various “client” tools included in the tool environment provide access to the repository and are focused on performing various tasks that arise during the design process.

To study and analyze source databases, a reengineering (reverse engineering) procedure is used, which automatically restores in the repository all metainformation about the schema and objects of any data source. To work with the received specifications and highlight the subset of tables and views of interest, use the database schema diagrammer.

This tool includes a convenient graphical editor for displaying data structures in the form of diagrams and allows you to enter additional information into the repository about the semantics and features of tables, columns and other objects.

Based on the results of the analysis of data sources and the information needs of users, a data warehouse is designed. This task is greatly facilitated by convenient visual design tools included in the database schema diagrammer, a wide range of tests for the completeness and consistency of the developed schema, automatic generation of various documentation, etc.

An important feature of the stage associated with creating a warehouse data schema is the use of a special design technique, the so-called star or snowflake schemas . Each such schema consists of a dedicated main table (fact table) , containing the values of one or more indicators, and several small reference tables, which are referenced by rows of the fact table. In this case, the fact table contained the values of two open position measures (spot and forward) for various combinations of column values that make up the primary key. The primary key columns are associated with reference tables, which include a currency directory, a date directory, a list of profit centers, etc.

For each table, the repository stores a lot of different meta information. Here you can specify various details of table storage, set the characteristics of the columns, and the list of these characteristics is wider than what can be included in the corresponding database creation program. An example is hardware support for domains or custom data types. Integrity constraints are also specified for tables.

An important feature of the Oracle Designer design tools, which distinguishes it from similar products from other companies, is the ability to specify in the repository not only standard logical-level objects - tables and views, but also various special objects of both the logical and physical levels. For example, when designing a storage facility, you can provide in advance for various optimization structures - indexes, clusters, etc., and determine the characteristics of table spaces. Of the logical level objects, specifications of users and user groups are useful.

After the main work on designing the storage facility is completed, a program for creating the storage structure is generated using a special utility. The programs are well structured: each type of object is assigned its own file, and before starting the procedure, you can specify which objects of this type should be created.

Oracle Designer tools help you do more than just create data warehouses. With their help, you can subsequently maintain and develop the repository, correct metainformation about old objects, and introduce new ones. To accomplish these tasks, Oracle Designer includes a number of special utilities and tools, from generating numerous reports that provide accurate technical documentation to utilities that compare real storage objects with their meta descriptions. As a result of this comparison, it is possible to generate a program that restructures the storage and brings real objects to their meta-description.

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